

Higher Education in India: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

India has excelled as a center of learning. Ancient universities of repute, like the Nalanda, Takshashila attracted scholars from different corners of the world. The ancient system of education in the Vedic and the Buddhist systems of education. The Medieval era led to the blending of cultures and the advent of the Madrasa as an important center of education. The British colonial rule in India grafted into the Indian society the system of education which was designed by the British for the maintenance of their imperial administration in India, called the Macaulay scheme of education. This forced inheritance made India feel the need for reconstruction far before independence, but it took effect post-independence. Now The world has realized that the economic success of the states is directly determined by their education systems. Education is a Nation's Strength. A developed nation is inevitably an educated nation. Indian higher education system is the third largest in the world, next to the United States and China. Since independence, India as a developing nation is contentiously progressing in the education field. Although there have been a lot of challenges to the higher education system of India equally have lot of opportunities to overcome these challenges and to make higher education system much better. It needs greater transparency and accountability, the role of colleges and universities in the new millennium, and emerging scientific research on how people learn is of utmost important. India needs well skilled and highly educated people who can drive our economy forward. India provides highly skilled people to other countries; therefore; it is very easy for India to transfer our country from a developing nation to a developed nation. The current study aims to highlight the challenges and to point out the opportunities in the higher education system in India.

Keywords: higher education policies Education, Opportunities, Challenges, Colleges, Universities.

Introduction

From time immemorial, India has excelled as a center of learning. Ancient universities of repute, like the Nalanda, Takshashila, Vikramshila and Vallabhi attracted scholars from different corners of the world. The ancient system of education in the Vedic period was marked by the Brahmanical and the Buddhist systems of education. The Medieval era led to the blending of cultures and the advent of the Madrasa as an important center of education. "Till the 18th century, India had three distinct traditions of advanced scholarship in the Hindu

gurukulas, the Buddhist viharas and the Quranicmadarsas.” (Agarwal, P., 2009) [1]. A major transformation came up in the Indian higher education through the initiatives of the British leaving both negative and positive impacts.

The colonial system of education in India was developed in three stages: (a) the efforts of the East India Company (1765-1813), (b) the efforts of the British Parliament (1813-1853); and (c) the educational efforts under direct British rule (1854-1947). The first phase was marked by the foundation of the Calcutta Madrassah in 1781 by Warren Hastings, followed by the establishment of the Benaras Sanskrit College in 1791 by Jonathan Duncan. During this period, English education had been gaining popularity with the efforts of missionaries. Lord Wellesley established the Fort William College for the training of youth civilians in 1800 and ushered in western education by bringing English officials and Indian Pandits together. Shortly, Raja Rammohan Roy launched a movement in favor of western learning and liberal education and founded the Hindu College in 1817, which was renamed Presidency College in June 1855. But the motive of the British was to graft into the Indian society the system of education which was designed by the British for the maintenance of their imperial administration in India. Consequently, Macaulay’s minute of February 1835 saw a rejection of the Orientalists and a bias in favor of spreading Western knowledge through the English language, thereby supporting the Anglicists. Both fortunately and unfortunately this decision has reverberated in Indian higher education through the nineteenth and twentieth centuries and has its echoes even in the twenty-first century.

This forced inheritance made India feel the need for reconstruction far before independence, but it took effect post-independence. Motivated by the able leadership of Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, the Indian system of higher education started expanding and was nourished time and again by various public policies and formation of different commissions and committees, like the University Education Commission (1948-49), foundation of the University Grants Commission (UGC) in 1956, Kothari Commission (1964-66), formulation of the first National Policy on Education (1968), and so on, till today, when an initiative of the Government of India is on to usher in and implement a New Education Policy. Sincerity has always reflected on the part of the Government of India at all times to improve the higher education system through apt policies. There has been unthinkable growth and expansion (as shown in Table 1) and today it has the status of being one of the largest educational systems in the world.

India’s higher education system is the world’s third largest in terms of students, next to China and the United States. In the future, India will be one of the largest education hubs. India’s Higher Education sector has witnessed a tremendous increase in the number of Universities/University level Institutions & Colleges since independence. The ‘Right to Education Act’ which stipulates compulsory and free education to all children within the age groups of 6-14 years, has brought about a revolution in the education system of the country with statistics revealing a staggering enrolment in schools over the last four years. The involvement of the private sector in higher education has seen drastic changes in the field. Today over 60% of higher education institutions in India are promoted by the private sector. This has accelerated the establishment of institutes which have originated over the last decade making India home to the largest number of Higher Education institutions in the world, with student enrolments at the second highest. The number of Universities has increased 34 times from 20 in 1950 to 677 in 2014. Despite these numbers, international education rating agencies have not placed many of these institutions within the best of the world ranking. Also, India has failed to produce world-class universities.

Today, Knowledge is power. The more knowledge one has, the more empowered one is. However, India continues to face stern challenges. Despite growing investment in education, 25 percent of its population is still illiterate; only 15 percent of Indian students reach high school and

just 7 percent graduate. The quality of education in India whether at primary or higher education is significantly poor as compared to major developing nations of the world. As of 2010, India's post-secondary institutions offer only enough seats for 7 percent of India's college-age population, 25 percent of teaching positions nationwide are vacant, and 57 percent of college professors lack either a master's or Ph.D. degree. As of 2016, there are 1820 degree-granting engineering colleges in India with an annual student intake of 685,000 (Science and Technology Education, 2016). However, these institutions face a shortage of faculty and concerns have been raised over the quality of education.

Despite these challenges higher education system of India equally, have a lot of opportunities to overcome these challenges and have the capability to make its identity at the international level. However, it needs greater transparency and accountability, the role of universities and colleges in the new millennium, and emerging scientific research on how people learn is of utmost important. India provides highly skilled people to other countries; therefore; it is very easy for India to transfer our country from a developing nation to a developed nation.

Growth of Higher Education Sector in India

As higher education systems grow and diversify, society is increasingly concerned about the quality of programmes, public assessments and international rankings of higher education institutions. However, these comparisons tend to overemphasize research, using research performance as a yardstick of institutional value. If these processes fail to address the quality of teaching, it is in part because measuring teaching quality is challenging (Hernard, 2008).

India has always been a land of scholars and learners. In ancient times also, India was regarded all over the world for its universities like Taxila, Nalanda, Vikramshila and its scholars. By independence, India had 20 universities, 500 colleges enrolling about 2,30,000 students. Since independence, India has progressed significantly in terms of higher education statistics. This number has increased to 659 Universities and 38252 colleges up to December 2015-16. Central Government and State Governments are trying to nurture talent by focusing on the number of Universities and Colleges for expansion of higher educations. There is no doubt to the fact that much of the progress achieved by India in education has come from the private sector. The public sector and private sector is not in opposition to each other, but they are working simultaneously in the Indian education sphere. UGC is the main governing body that enforces the standards, advises the government and helps coordinate between center and states.

Challenges in Higher Education in India

It is our 69th year of independence; still our education system has not been developed fully. We are not able to list a single university in the top 100 universities of the world. Various governments changed during these six decades. They tried to boost the education system and implemented various education policies, but they were not sufficient to put an example for the universe. UGC is continuously working and focusing on quality education in the higher education sector. Still, we are facing a lot of problems and challenges in our education system. Some of the basic challenges in the higher education system in India are discussed below:

Enrolment: The Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) of India in higher education is only 15% which is quite low as compared to the developed as well as, other developing countries. With the increase of enrolments at the school level, the supply of higher education institutes is insufficient to meet the growing demand in the country.

Equity: There is no equity in GER among different sects of society. According to previous studies, GER in higher education in India among male and female varies to a greater extent. There

are regional variations too some states have high GER while as some is quite behind the national GER which reflects a significant imbalances within the higher education system.

Quality: Quality in higher education is a multi-dimensional, multilevel, and a dynamic concept. Ensuring quality in higher education is amongst the foremost challenges being faced in India today. However, the Government is continuously focusing on quality education. Still, a Large number of colleges and universities in India are unable to meet the minimum requirements laid down by the UGC and our universities are not in a position to mark its place among the top universities of the world.

Infrastructure: Poor infrastructure is another challenge to the higher education system of India particularly the institutes run by the public sector suffer from poor physical facilities and infrastructure. There are a large number of colleges which are functioning on the second or third floor of the building on the ground, or the first floor there exists readymade hosieries or photocopy shops.

Political interference: Most of the educational Institutions are owned by the political leaders, who are playing a key role in governing bodies of the Universities. They are using innocent students for their selfish means. Students organize campaigns, forget their objectives and begin to develop their careers in politics.

Faculty: Faculty shortages and the inability of the state educational system to attract and retain well-qualified teachers have been posing challenges to quality education for many years. Large numbers of NET /Ph.D. candidates are unemployed even there are a lot of vacancies in higher education, these deserving candidates are then applying in other departments which is the biggest blow to the higher education system.

Accreditation: As per the data provided by the NAAC, as of June 2010, “not even 25% of the total higher education institutions in the country were accredited. And among those accredited, only 30% of the universities and 45% of the colleges were found to be of quality to be ranked at ‘A’ level”.

Research and Innovation: there are very nominal scholars in our country whose writing is cited by famous western authors. There is an inadequate focus on research in higher education institutes. There are insufficient resources and facilities, as well as, limited numbers of quality faculty to advice students. Most of the research scholars are without fellowships or not getting their fellowships on time which directly or indirectly affects their research. Moreover, Indian Higher education institutions are poorly connected to research centers. So, this is another area of challenge to higher education in India.

Structure of higher education: Management of the Indian education faces challenges of over-centralisation, bureaucratic structures and lack of accountability, transparency, and professionalism. As a result of the increase in a number of affiliated colleges and students, the burden of administrative functions of universities has significantly increased and the core focus on academics and research is diluted (Kumar, 2015).

Opportunities in Higher Education

India is a large country, with an estimated population of young people aged between 18 to 23 years to be around 150 million. The sheer size of the market offers huge opportunities for the development of the higher education sector in India. India now boasts of having more than 33,000 colleges and 854 universities, which has been quite a remarkable growth during the last six decades. The year 2015 witnessed 23.4 million enrollments, which makes India the 3rd largest educational system in the world. Unfortunately, the educational infrastructure of India is inadequate to handle such huge volumes. In spite of all the government spending in the educational sector, it is just too

insufficient to meet the growing requirements. Therefore, the Higher Education sector has now been identified as one of the promising areas for private and foreign investments. It offers immense investment opportunities in both non-regulated and regulated segments.

Indian higher education system is growing very fast irrespective of various challenges, but there is no reason that these Challenges cannot be overcome. With the help of new-age learning tools, it is easy for a country like India to overcome these problems and bring a paradigm shift in the country's higher education sector. With such a vibrant country with a huge population properly educated, the possibilities are endless. If knowledge is imparted using advanced digital teaching and learning tools, and society is made aware of where we are currently lagging, our country can easily emerge as one of the most developed nations in the world.

There are opportunities for strategic engagement and capacity building in higher education leadership and management at the state level. There are opportunities for India to collaborate at national and international level on areas of systemic reform, including quality assurance, international credit recognition, and unified national qualifications framework. Equality of educational opportunity in higher education is considered essential because higher education is a powerful tool for reducing or eliminating income and wealth disparities. The idea of equalizing educational opportunities also lies in the fact that "the ability to profit by higher education is spread among all classes of people. There are great reserves of untapped ability in the society; if offered the chance they can rise to the top. A great deal of talent of the highest level is lost by an in the egalitarian system of education".

Suggestions for Improving the System of Higher Education

There is a need to implement innovative and transformational approach from primary to higher education level to make the Indian educational system globally more relevant and competitive.

Higher educational institutes need to improve quality and reputation.

There should be a good infrastructure of colleges and universities which may attract the students.

The government must promote collaboration between Indian higher education institutes and top International institutes and also generate linkage between national research laboratories and research centers of top institutions for better quality and collaborative research.

There is a need to focus on the graduate students by providing them such courses in which they can achieve excellence, gain a deeper knowledge of the subject so that they will get jobs after recruitment in the companies which would reduce unnecessary rush to the higher education.

Universities and colleges in both public-private must be away from the political affiliations, Favouritism; money making process should be out of education system, etc.

There should be a multidisciplinary approach in higher education so that students knowledge may not be restricted only to his subjects.

Conclusion

As a concluding remark, it must be mentioned that the rich tradition of excellence in higher education that was initiated in the ancient era, has continued over time in India, and post-independence India has witnessed tremendous effort by the Government of India and also the State governments to sustain this richness in higher education in the country. The period from 1947 to 1986 was a period of massive improvement in higher education. 1986 onwards, for quite a long period there was a slump in progress in higher education, though this period experienced massive privatization in the field of higher education in India. But before the pendulum could swing too far, higher education has again become one of the most important agenda for the Government of India, which is now actively involved in bringing about the colossal transformation of the system through effective reforms, and the New Education Policy would hopefully be successful in this attempt.

Education is a process by which a person's body, mind and character are formed and strengthened. It is bringing of head, heart and mind together and thus enabling a person to develop an all-round personality identifying the best in him or her. Higher education in India has expanded very rapidly in the last six decades after independence yet it is not equally accessible to all. India is today one of the fastest developing countries of the world with the annual growth rate going above 9%. Still, a large section of the population remains illiterate and a large number of children's do not get even primary education. This is not only excluded a large section of the population from contributing to the development of the country fully, but it has also prevented them from utilizing the benefits of whatever development have taken place for the benefit of the people. No doubt India is facing various challenges in higher education but to tackle these challenges and to boost higher education is utmost important. India is a country of huge human resource potential, to utilize this potential properly is the issue which needed to discuss. Opportunities are available but how to get benefits from these opportunities and how to make them accessible to others is a matter of concern. To sustain that rate of growth, there is a need to increase the number of institutes and also the quality of higher education in India. To reach and achieve the future requirements there is an urgent need to relook at the Financial Resources, Access and Equity, Quality Standards, Relevance, infrastructure and at the end the Responsiveness.

References

1. Agarwal P. Indian Higher Education - Envisioning the Future, New Delhi, India: SAGE Publications Pvt. Ltd, 2009.
2. Anandkrishnan M. Critique of Knowledge Commission, Economic and Political Weekly, Vol. 2007; 42(7):557-560.
3. Choudhary RP. EIQG: New Horizon of Indian Higher Education, the BESC Journal of Commerce and Management, 2015, 7-16.
4. Deshpande S. Higher Education An Uncertain Policy Process, Economic and Political Weekly, 2016; L1(35): 37-43.
5. Education Commission of Education and National Development. Report of the Education Commission, 1964-66: National Council of Educational Research and Training, New Delhi, 1966.
6. Hatekar N. Changing Higher Education Scenario in India", Economic and Political Weekly, 2009; XLIV(38): 22-23.
7. Shaguri, Obadya Ray, Higher Education in India Access, Equity, Quality, EAN World Congress Scholar, Global Access to Postsecondary Education, 2013.
8. Masani, Zareer, India still Asia's reluctant tiger, BBC Radio 4, 27 February 2008. Newsweek, Special Report: The Education Race, August 18-25, 2011.
9. Science and Technology Education". Press Information Bureau, Retrieved 2009 08-08 Mitra, Sramana, How To Save The World's Back Office of Forbes, 03.14.2008.
10. MHRD Reports 2015.

Web Sources

1. <http://www.educationalnetwork.online/>
2. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1131773.pdf>
3. <http://educationdiveuce.org/education/opportunities-in-higher-education>